

HORIZON EUROPE

Data Management Plan

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

DMP History of Changes

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V02	22-01-2026	Titus Hjelm	Comments from supervisor
V03	10-02-2026	Titus Hjelm	Version submitted

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WOMEN'S SPIRITUALITY
AS A SOURCE OF CREATIVITY
IN POPULAR MUSIC

UNIVERSITY OF HELSINKI

Project Name: Women's Spirituality as a Source of Creativity in Popular Music

Project Acronym: [SHE SHE](#)

Project Researcher: Susana González Martínez, PhD. **ORCID iD:** 0000-0003-2345-258X

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Affiliation: University of Helsinki

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Project Abstract:

This research examines how spirituality can expand creativity in women's contributions to popular music. Women's spiritual explorations bring together some of the most important political and religious dimensions of contemporary life, but their research treatment remains confined to the status of sexualized Other. This research focuses on the unvetted artistic languages women use to express spirituality to yield a new understanding of the role of spirituality on creativity and the contributions of women as creative agents, analyzing metal and hip-hop music to understand: (1) the interrelation of spirituality with women's identity, (2) how spirituality affects their perceptions of the music as dialectical language, and (3) the influence that spirituality has on their creativity and production process. The researcher will implement an interdisciplinary, participatory methodology to analyze 10 case studies and conduct 10 interviews with musicians. The researcher and the reflection group (formed by the study participants) will meet via Zoom sessions to discuss the research findings and co-write articles. These techniques will be leveraged alongside theoretical considerations for studying religions, including Critical Discursive Study of Religions—developed by Prof. Hjelm—to guide a discursive analysis of lyrics, videos, and performances. The study will contribute to making women's artistic spiritual practice visible and expand understanding of the articulation between spirituality, identity, and creativity in popular music through a comprehensive analytical perspective that includes the musical process as a whole.

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1. DATA SUMMARY

1.1. Data summary

Types of data generated or reused

The [SHE SHE](#) project adheres to a standardized workflow for data collection, processing, and analysis that follows FAIR principles, emphasizing transparency, accessibility, replicability, and ethical responsibility. The research is based on a combination of qualitative interviews, reflection group sessions, and case-study analysis of a multimodal artistic corpus.

The legal basis for data processing is participants' consent, and all participants understand that their data cannot be fully anonymized because they are contributors to the study. As contributors, participants will generate and analyze data, disseminate findings, and coauthor articles. Each participant has signed: 1) a participation consent form, and 2) an ethical consent form, granting permission for their personal data to be publicly published as contributors to the study. While the study acknowledges participants as contributors in the research outputs (e.g., articles, project website), the researcher and project supervisor have opted to pseudonymize participants in the datasets to prevent specific thoughts from being directly attributed to individuals in the interviews and reflection group sessions. This approach allows the analysis to focus on the ideas expressed rather than on who articulated them, and it makes datasets openly publishable and reusable.

I. Qualitative interviews: Ten in-depth interviews will be conducted via Zoom with women artists who openly express their spirituality through metal music and hip-hop. The group of participants includes subjects from the Global North and the Global South.

- Sensitive and personal data: The interview transcripts will be pseudonymized to uphold participants' privacy rights and ensure data protection. Additionally, any sensitive information will be paraphrased before archiving and publication.
- File format:
 - Video and audio recordings will be stored in MP4 and M4A.
 - Pseudonymized transcripts will be stored in PDF/A.
- Size estimated: ~10GB.

II. Reflection group sessions: Three reflection group sessions will be carried out via Zoom with participants to discuss the research questions based on the initial findings from the interviews and co-write articles.

- Sensitive and personal data: The reflection group session transcripts will be pseudonymized, and sensitive data paraphrased before archiving and publication.
- File format:

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- Video and audio recordings will be stored in MP4 and M4A.
- Pseudonymized transcripts will be stored in PDF/A.

- Size estimated: ~2.5GB.

III- Analytical data of multimodal artistic corpora: a derived metadata collection in CSV format, documenting analytical features of three sub-corpora: 10 music videos, 10 song lyrics, and 10 images. The CSV file links to external sources via URLs.

- Sensitive data and copyright: The authors of the artistic works analyzed are the project participants, who have granted permission for the study to use their artistic materials without restriction. However, to ensure data reusability and to respect third parties' intellectual property rights, such as those of record labels, the dataset will not redistribute protected content. Instead, it will offer derivative analyses and include direct links to the artistic sources.
- File Format: CSV (UTF-8) linked to the original sources.
- Size Estimated: ~6KB

Total data volume: Approximately 13GB for primary and processed data.

Data controller: University of Helsinki

Ownership and other agreements:

Data ownership resides with the University of Helsinki and the researchers' project. The granting authority (the European Commission and any other EU service) has the right to use any material, documentation, and information for policy, information, communication, dissemination, and public purposes. The data will be managed in accordance with the University of Helsinki policies on research data and intellectual property. Before project completion, datasets and related materials will be deposited in an open-access repository with DOIs assigned.

Consistency and quality of data:

Data quality and consistency will be ensured through rigorous documentation, standardized protocols, and multiple layers of verification across all work packages. All data collection, processing, and analysis will follow a standardized workflow emphasizing transparency, replicability, and ethical responsibility. The project will collect only the minimum personal data necessary for its purposes.

- Interview guides will adhere to a consistent structure across all interviews to ensure thematic coherence while allowing contextual flexibility. Interviews from English-speaking participants will be transcribed verbatim and subsequently coded using a qualitative codebook developed iteratively through collaboration between the researcher and the supervisor. Interviews from Spanish-speaking participants will be translated into English by the researcher and transcribed literally (word by word), preserving the grammatical structure of the original as much as possible. They will subsequently be coded using a qualitative codebook developed iteratively through collaboration between the researcher and the supervisor.
- Reflection group session guides will adhere to a consistent structure across all sessions following an ECRO methodology (Conceptual Referential Operational Schema, CROS) for group dynamics. The sessions will be held

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in English and will use subtitles for Spanish-speaking participants who need them. The recorded sessions will be transcribed verbatim and subsequently coded using a qualitative codebook developed iteratively through collaboration between the researcher and the supervisor.

- Multimedia artistic corpora analytical guides will adhere to a consistent structure for corpus definition (scope, selection, formats) and analytical processing across textual, visual, and intertextual levels. The three sub-corpora (music videos, song lyrics, and images) will be coded using a qualitative codebook developed iteratively through collaboration between the researcher and the supervisor.

Data documentation

Data documentation and metadata will adhere to academic and technical standards to ensure transparency and reproducibility across all data types.

General Documentation Practices:

- All datasets will include a structured "readme.md" file describing the dataset's content, structure, methodology, provenance, ethical considerations, and citation requirements.
- All datasets will include a "DDI-Codebook.xml" file that follows the Data Documentation Initiative standards for Social Sciences data.
- Each data type will be assigned a persistent identifier (DOI).
- File formats will prioritize open standards (.csv, .json, .xml).
- Interview dataset: Each interview transcript will include pseudonymization notes, interview metadata, and consent status.
- Reflection group dataset: Each reflection group session will include pseudonymization notes, session metadata, and consent status.
- All datasets will include a "metadata.jsonld" file (linked data) using the Qualified Dublin Core and LC (Library of Congress) controlled vocabularies to improve harvesting and indexing of content.
- All datasets will include a file history table to track versions and document any changes.
- All datasets will be published in open access.
- The DMP will be updated in line with project progress and the data lifecycle.

Data purpose:

The data generated by the study, together with the analysis of artistic corpora, are vital to achieving the research objectives 01, 02, and 03 outlined in the research proposal. Notably, the information collected from interviews and reflection group sessions will provide essential insights for addressing the research questions. Furthermore, analyzing the artistic sources of the selected 10 case studies is imperative for conducting a Critical Discursive Study of Religion.

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Data utility:

The research data will serve as a valuable resource for scholars investigating the relationships between women's spirituality and creativity as expressed in popular music. Moreover, it is likely to interest researchers and educators in fields such as music, gender studies, and religious studies. The data will also be of interest to those engaged in participatory research methodologies within the Social Sciences and Citizen Science. Additionally, the general public interested in this topic will find the datasets informative and relevant.

2. FAIR DATA

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

The data documentation adheres to DDI (Data Documentation Initiative) standards to promote methodological transparency and interoperability in the Social Sciences. This structure will be incorporated into a metadata schema for each dataset, organized around the following technical pillars, thereby improving the findability and interoperability of the research data:

-Schema and format: The metadata will use a JSON-LD (Linked Data) structure, which will establish a direct semantic connection between local data and the global semantic web standard.

-Standardization: The metadata will use Qualified Dublin Core elements to enable more nuanced descriptions of resources. This includes clear distinctions among data types, such as creation, modification, and publication, as well as definitions of different contribution roles. All metadata documentation will consist of information on data sources, collection methods, and preprocessing pipelines for complete transparency.

-Specialized controlled vocabularies and keywords: to ensure terminological precision and eliminate ambiguities, the classification will utilize three systems from the Library of Congress: LCSH (Library of Congress Subject Headings) for subject content, LCGFT (Library of Congress Genre/Form Terms) to describe the formal attributes of the resource, and the LCMPT (Library of Congress Medium of Performance Thesaurus for Music) for the precise description of music instrumentation and performance methods. Furthermore, each dataset will be accompanied by keywords to enhance its discoverability and promote potential reuse through CESSDA CVs.

-Identification and traceability: Each dataset will be assigned a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) to ensure its permanent identification/citation. Data integrity will be maintained using Semantic Version Control integrated into the metadata, along with a systematic naming convention for files. Additionally, each dataset will include a file history table to track versions and provide details of any changes made.

This rich metadata scheme fully integrates with the Web of Data. This approach will allow both human users and algorithms to interpret information easily and independently, while providing global linguistic standardization that preserves long-term integrity and traceability. The scheme effectively balances the precision of controlled vocabularies with the flexibility of keywords, optimizing taxonomic accuracy while facilitating the use of emerging terminological trends in the field. This metadata scheme will ensure high-fidelity data harvesting, enabling international aggregators (e.g., Google Scholar, OpenAIRE) to index content with exceptional accuracy, thereby maximizing visibility, relevance, and scientific impact.

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2.2. Making data accessible

Accessibility, trusted repositories, and permanence:

- Dataset formats will prioritize open standards (.csv, .jsonld, .xml, .pdf/a) to ensure interoperability.
- Datasets will be published with open access in the ZENODO repository.
- Metadata will include information to enable the user access to data and will be stored in the University of Helsinki Data Catalogue, which harvests metadata directly from the ZENODO repository.
- Metadata will consistently remain accessible through Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), even after the associated data is no longer available. This will ensure that users can continue to reference and retrieve crucial contextual information about the data.

Persistent identifiers and license:

- Datasets will be assigned persistent identifiers (DOIs) through the ZENODO repository.
- Datasets will be under the CC BY 4.0 license.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Standards and practices for interoperability:

DDI standards in Social Sciences formats and methodologies, and CESSDA best practices for interoperability will be implemented. The SHE SHE project will ensure interoperability of the data through the following practices:

- Datasets will be interconnected through the schema "IsBasedOn" and the Dublin Core term "dcterms:relation", facilitating seamless navigation between different project data and derived data.
- The data documentation will provide a rich context through metadata and DDI-codebooks to enable exchange and reuse across disciplines.
- The implementation of controlled and specific vocabularies, including Library of Congress (LC), Library of Congress Genre/Form Terms (LCGFT), and Library of Congress Medium of Performance Thesaurus for Music (LCMPT), facilitates global linguistic standardization, thereby ensuring interoperability across various platforms and systems.
- The use of combined file formats (.xlm, .csv, .pdf/a, and .md) ensures interoperability, facilitating processing in other disciplines of the Social Sciences and Digital Humanities.

2.4. Increase data reuse

Practices for data reusability:

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The data reusability will be ensured through the following practices:

- All datasets will provide a structured "readme.md" file describing the dataset content, provenance, structure, methodology, analysis, control version, ethical considerations, consent status, and citation requirements.
- Codebooks will be archived in each dataset and will follow DDI and CESSDA standards for qualitative data.
- Metadata in the "metadata.jsonld" file format will provide rich contextual information about data collection, methods, and analysis.
- All datasets will be disseminated with open access through the project website to the general public.
- The dataset qualitative interviews transcripts will include pseudonymization notes, and each transcript will include interview metadata (setting, language, region, date) and consent status.
- The dataset reflection group sessions transcripts will include pseudonymization notes, and each transcript will include session metadata (date, theme, setting, language) and consent status.
- The analytical dataset of multimodal artistic corpora: a derived metadata collection will include links to the original sources for replicability, notes about variable definitions, and metadata of each source (source, author, date, publication outlet, and collection method).

3. OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

3.1. Other research outputs

The [SHE SHE](#) project aims to produce three articles for publication in open-access journals, along with a minimum of two presentations—one at an international conference and another at a University of Helsinki event designed for the general public. Both the published articles and any audiovisual materials generated from the presentations will be archived in the ZENODO repository and will include their own metadata.

Additionally, the [SHE SHE](#) project will develop a website and a virtual gallery to disseminate the study and its findings in accordance with the UH Research Lawyers for copyright-related questions. The metadata for both the project's website and virtual gallery will be created and deposited in the ZENODO repository.

By establishing clear connections to the project's associated datasets, this metadata will provide a robust framework that ensures the outputs are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). This approach will enhance the visibility and utility of the project's results for researchers and the wider community.

4. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

4.1. Allocation of resources

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Data management responsibilities:

Susana González Martínez, the project researcher, will be responsible for data management, compliance, analysis, and version control under the supervision of Prof. Titus Hjelm.

Allocation of resources:

Data management will utilize the University of Helsinki's services for secure storage, metadata creation, and long-term preservation. The University of Helsinki supports the resources for data documentation, analysis, and metadata preparation. The personnel for data management are within the MSCA project.

There are no additional costs associated with using the ZENODO repository. Any open-access publication fees linked to the research outputs (articles) will be covered by the MSCA funding allocated to the project's research costs or by the University of Helsinki. Additionally, the costs of creating the project's website and virtual gallery will be covered by the MSCA research budget.

After the project's completion, the website and virtual gallery will continue to be maintained in accordance with the University of Helsinki's policies for long-term preservation.

5. DATA SECURITY

5.1. Data security

Storage during the research project:

All project data will be securely stored on the University of Helsinki's institutional research data infrastructure, which complies with EU GDPR, Finnish Data Protection Act (1050/1018), and the University's Information Security Policy.

-The primary storage environment will be the University's secure cloud servers (OneDrive) and internal drives with access restricted to project users' roles, and the UH Group Folder (P-Drive), which offers strong data protection, daily backup, and version control.

-Qualitative interviews and reflection group sessions (transcripts, pseudonymized files, and consent forms) will be stored separately from metadata and analysis outputs to prevent re-identification.

-Data will not be transferred outside the EU.

Backup and security procedures:

All data stored at the University of Helsinki servers is automatically backed up daily, with multiple redundant copies maintained at separate physical locations in Finland.

-Sensitive or in-progress files will have a local encrypted backup in external drives, updated weekly, and stored in secure, access-controlled premises.

-Version control systems (UH internal repositories) will provide an additional layer of backup for metadata.

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-Access to project data will be restricted to the researcher and the supervisor of the project and managed through the University of Helsinki's secure authentication system using institutional logins and two-factor authentication.

-All sensitive files (interviews and reflection group sessions materials) will be stored in encrypted folders.

Trusted repositories:

-All metadata will be archived in the University of Helsinki Data Catalogue.

-All datasets and metadata will be published in the ZENODO repository for long-term preservation and curation (as long as the repository exists, for at least 20 years).

6. ETHICS

6. 1. Ethics

Compliance with ethical principles and relevant legislation:

The project researchers will ensure that the research and data management comply with the principles of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, 2016/679), the Finnish Data Protection Act (1050/2018), and the ethical standards of the University of Helsinki. Responsible Conduct of Research Code and the Guidelines for Good Scientific Practices and Procedures for Handling Misconduct and Fraud in Science of the Finnish National Board on Research Integrity TENK, the European Code of Conduct of Research Integrity, European Textbook on Ethics in Research, WMA Declaration of Helsinki Ethical Principles at the University of Helsinki, and the University of Helsinki Social Media Guidelines.

The research will be conducted in accordance with established ethical principles aimed at protecting human participants from harm, as outlined by the European Commission and the University of Helsinki. In particular, the following:

- Respecting human dignity and integrity
- Ensuring honesty and transparency towards research subjects
- Respecting individual autonomy and obtaining free and informed consent
- Protecting vulnerable individuals
- Ensuring privacy and confidentiality
- Promoting justice and inclusiveness

Ethical practices of the research for data management:

The research project presents minimal risk to participants, who are artists expressing and publicly sharing their spiritual or religious views through their artistic works. The ethical practices governing project data management will

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ensure the protection of participants' private information. This includes safeguarding privacy and implementing appropriate measures at all stages of data processing, handling, and storage throughout the research process and beyond.

The following practices guide the ethical consideration of the research data management:

-The researcher responsible for data management has attended advanced data management and ethical research training at the University of Helsinki before the start of the research.

-The project will collect only the minimum personal data for its purposes.

-A preliminary ethical evaluation was conducted to assess the necessity of a subsequent ethical statement from the University of Helsinki Research Ethics Committee (REC) in the Humanities and Social and Behavioural Sciences. The preliminary evaluation confirmed that the study adheres to ethical standards for several reasons: 1) the participants are public artists expressing their personal religious views through their artistic work, 2) all participants have signed consent forms, 3) the participants are not classified as vulnerable individuals, 4) the study presents minimal risk to participants, and 5) the thematic focus of the study is on the interconnections between spirituality and creativity rather than on the religious beliefs themselves.

-The study documentation—comprising 1) information sheet, 2) data protection note, 3) participation consent form, 4) ethical consent form, and 5) DMP—has undergone review by specialists from Data Management/Protection Services at the University of Helsinki.

-Participants were provided with comprehensive information in an accessible language concerning the research purposes and methods, participation as contributors, publication in open access of the project data for scientific reuse, and their rights related to data protection. They were given sufficient time to review the documentation and ask any questions they may have had.

-The participants have signed two distinct consent forms: 1) a participation consent form to participate in the study, and 2) an ethical consent form for the open publication of their data as contributors to the study.

-The participants will be acknowledged as study contributors on the project's website and the virtual gallery, as well as coauthors in any subsequent scholarly articles.

-The participants' personal data will be pseudonymized in the interviews and reflection group sessions transcripts, and any sensitive data will be paraphrased before publication and long-term archiving to protect the privacy of their opinions and adhere to the data protection legislation.

These measures collectively signify a commitment to ethical research practices that adhere to the principles established in the EU Research Charter of Fundamental Rights and the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union concerning data protection. This commitment aligns with the EU Ethics Guide for the Social Sciences and Humanities, which emphasizes safeguarding participants' rights throughout the study's duration and beyond.

7. OTHER ISSUES

7.1. Other issues

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The project will not use any national, funder, sectoral, or departmental data management processes beyond those outlined in this Data Management Plan (DMP).

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